

The Model of Organizational Justice and Talent Management on Work Engagement

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ONOMÁZEIN 61 (September 2023): 107-115

ISSN: 0718-5758

Abstract

Using quantitative research, this study looks into how organizational justice and talent management affect employee job involvement. Conducted on 20 road construction companies in DKI Jakarta, this study used 80 respondents and SEM-PLS approach for processing. Results reveal that in organizations belonging to road construction companies in DKI Jakarta Province, organizational justice has a direct impact on employee work involvement, while talent management directly influences it.

Keywords: Organizational Justice, Talent Management and Job Engagement.

1. Introduction

The road contractor service industry relies heavily on motivated and involved employees to succeed. A crucial aspect of this industry is providing top-notch service to clients. Organizational success is highly dependent on motivated and involved staff who are encouraged to go above and beyond in their duties, knowing that the achievements of the organization will benefit its employees.

By examining the number of employees who leave within a given timeframe, we can gauge the extent of motivation and involvement in their work. Those who exhibit high involvement in their work tend to place greater emphasis on it, ultimately leading to stronger commitment and motivation. Due to the influential role played by employees in determining an organization's effectiveness, it becomes crucial to nurture job involvement. Modern-day organizations are faced with mounting challenges that necessitate the optimization of employee performance to stay competitive. Success or failure of an organization is heavily influenced by work motivation and involvement in human resources. The correct encouragement can lead employees to believe that an organization's success will also benefit them, thus motivating them to carry out their responsibilities. A critical factor that must not be overlooked.

One of the key components of employee work satisfaction is the urge, both mentally and physically, to perform tasks with a purpose (Mullins, 2016:221; Robbins and Judge, 2018:33; Gibson, et al, 2012:126; Schermerhorn, et al, 2010:10; Luthans, 2011:157; McShane & Glinow, 2018:22). Cooper and Makin (1995) have highlighted the importance of work motivation in determining individual success on the job. When an employee has high levels of work motivation, they are more likely to be enthusiastic and achieve organizational goals. Improving work motivation among employees is key to facilitating their productivity and enthusiasm in achieving optimum results (Prabu, 2005). In practice, employees with high motivation tend to maximize workplace performance, compared to their less motivated colleagues (Ghasafar, 2011). To fuel employee morale and foster loyalty, it's crucial to tailor motivational factors to individual preferences and needs (Karyono, 2008). This also enhances employees' efficiency and effectiveness, thereby leading to improved work output (Karyono, 2008).

Making employees motivated to work is a complex task, as noted by Armstrong (2008). It requires accommodating and acquiring the key factors that influence motivation, which include organizational commitment, job involvement, and job satisfaction. According to Freyedon (2012), job satisfaction, job involvement, and organizational commitment have a strong and positive relationship with work motivation. Additionally, factors such as empowerment, talent management, organizational justice, and work involvement are also influential in impacting one's motivation towards work.

The extent to which individuals perceive performance as important is closely connected to job involvement, which is a level of active participation in work. This has a direct bearing on their self-esteem. Being enthusiastic about their work and caring about the field are characteristic traits of employees who have high job involvement. According to Chungthai (2008), such individuals are more motivated and productive.

2. Literature review

Organizational Justice

Perceptions of fairness and equality in the workplace, also known as organizational justice, vary among researchers. While Gibson and colleagues (2012) define it as feeling treated equally in one's organization, Colquitt and co-authors (2009) propose it as a fair perception of individuals. Purwanto and Bagyo (2019) emphasize the relevance of work-related equality and fairness. Meanwhile, Celik and Sariturk (2012) point to the importance of worker perception of workplace applications. Apriono, et al (2021) suggest that organizational justice is linked to the perception of fairness that organizational members possess concerning the performance and results they obtain. On the other hand, Chone-Charash and Spector (2001) express that organizational justice is a perception rooted in the state of the employees, characterized by adequate treatment, accurate and sufficient information, and reasonable resources and rewards.

Employees' perception of being treated fairly and equally by their superiors is what defines organizational justice. It is closely tied to the work environment and the level of respect that employees receive from their colleagues. Therefore, it is crucial for organizations to create a culture that promotes fairness and equal treatment among employees in order to achieve better productivity and employee satisfaction.

Talent Management

The strategic management of Talent is elaborated on by Collings and Mellahi (2009), who spotlight the need for identifying sustainable and competitive advantageous key positions within an organization in a systematic manner. Primarily, the development of organizational talent to fill these critical roles is one of the significant responsibilities of this management style. The deployment of a Talent Management system can significantly influence organizational performance by strengthening work motivation, organizational commitment, and employee over-representation behavior. However, Capelli (2008) has a different take on the subject, stating that anticipating human resource needs ahead of time and constructing a fulfilling plan is at the core of Talent Management. Describing talent management as a means of boosting workplace productivity through system and process enhancement, Saha and Srivastava (2012) assert that its objective is the acquisition, development, retention, and alignment of necessary skills and abilities with present and future business demands. Ahuja and Ranga (2020) offer a corresponding definition, characterizing talent management as a strategic exercise in placing and nurturing personnel for maximum performance and in alignment with organizational objectives. Nawangsari and Sutawidjaya (2019) define Talent Management as a strategy that organizes human resources to draw in, enrich, encourage, and preserve active and committed employees. Lockwood (2006) describes it as a system or strategy aimed at lifting the productivity of the workplace through the design of better approaches to attract, develop, keep and deploy individuals with the needed skills and abilities to meet both present and future business requirements. This process comprises of identifying unoccupied positions, hiring fitting personnel, enhancing their skills and knowledge to match such positions, and retaining them to realize extended business goals.

Talent management, as explained, encompasses a set of strategic procedures implemented by organizations to acquire and nurture skilled and valuable employees through recruitment and other methods. This leads to the overall development of the organization.

Work Engagement

Employees who are engaged go beyond the call of duty to bring positive results for their organization. According to Hewitt Associates (2004), this energy and passion is a crucial measure of organizational success. Similarly, Schaufeli and Baker (2001) define work involvement as the integration of dedication, enthusiasm, and hard work to derive pleasure from the task at hand. In essence, engaged employees are those who remain loyal, spread positivity, and give their best to deliver excellence. Employee productivity and talent retention are greatly affected by engagement, which involves employees utilizing themselves in their work roles both physically and mentally. It is seen as an emotional and intellectual commitment to organizational groups, as noted by Falcone (2006). Those who are engaged are highly enthusiastic when it comes to their assigned job responsibilities, being fully participative throughout. This disclosure by Kim and Mauborge (2005:175) places employee involvement as the ultimate factor in talent retention. Personal involvement is defined by Khan (1990:694) in terms of how individuals express themselves during role performance. Involving employees in the strategic process is seen as a type of engagement that is separate from their attitudes and behaviors. This engagement is considered a part of a "fair process" that includes clear expectations and explanations. According to research, individuals are equally concerned with the fairness of the process as they are with the result. It has been suggested that proper protocol and procedures could affect people's attitudes and actions.

Organizational members attempt to exploit their role and the conditions of their engagement through job involvement, as seen in the aforementioned explanation. This involvement manifests in physical, cognitive, and emotional expressions during role performance. As such, one can conclude that job involvement is a way for individuals to make the most of their position within the organization.

Theoretical Framework

According to research by Apriono et al (2021), there exists a correlation between organizational justice and employee work involvement. This is in line with the findings of Sarawati and Lie (2021) who suggest that employees feel more involved with their work when their organization treats them with fairness. Dong et al's (2017) study supports the notion that organizational justice has a positive and noteworthy impact on employee job involvement. Similarly, Farid et al (2019) have affirmed that organizational justice holds a positive and substantial effect on employee job involvement. Further evidence of this can be found in Inoue et al's (2009) research, which establishes a causative link between organizational justice and employee job involvement. It was noted by Pirzada, et al (2020) that employee job involvement is positively and significantly impacted by organizational justice. Similarly, research conducted by Siu, et al (2016) found that organizational justice has a positive effect on employee work involvement. According to Storm, et al (2014), employee job involvement is positively affected by organizational justice.

In 2019, Ali and colleagues made mention that employee engagement could be impacted by talent management. Goestjahjanti and colleagues concurred in 2020, stating that talent management was indeed linked to employee engagement. Mohammed's research from 2015 has similarly suggested such a correlation. Mugizi and colleagues went on to explain this relationship in further detail in 2020. Additionally, Sadeli's 2017 study found that employee engagement could be influenced by talent management. This has been reinforced by Barkhuizen and colleagues' research in 2014. Alrowwadi and Wahba's studies both assert that talent management affects employee engagement. Wahba's research from 2016 and a more recent study by Alrowwadi et al. reach this same conclusion. The impact of talent management on employee engagement is a common topic among researchers, as evidenced by the frequent citations of these two studies.

3. Research Methodology

Utilizing an explanatory approach through quantitative methods, this analysis examines the population of workers belonging to a contractor company in the DKI Jakarta Province. Obtaining 80 respondents from 20 different road construction firms within the same province, the sample adheres to statistical analysis regulations. To collect data, a questionnaire with a Likert scale was utilized. Interpretations of the acquired data were completed with Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), applying a Partial Least Square (PLS) method. The hypothesis formulated for this analysis states:

Table 1. Research Hypotesis

No.	Hypothesis
H1	Organizational justice has a direct influence on work engagement
H2	Talent management has a direct influence on work engagement

4. Result and Discussion

Validity and Reliability

Table 2. Outer Model Evaluation

Variables	Sub-Variables	Cross Loading	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Critical Value
Organizational Justice	Distributive Justice	0.805	0.885	0.793	1.0000
	Procedural Justice	0.790	0.923	0.858	1.0000
	Interactive Justice	0.783	0.933	0.765	1.0000
Talent Management	Talent Attraction	0.682	0.943	0.891	1.0000
	Talent Development	0.770	0.831	0.710	1.0000
	Talent Retention	0.745	0.866	0.763	1.0000
Work Engagement	Trust and Integrity	0.797	0.885	0.793	1.0000
	Nature of Work	0.842	0.828	0.706	1.0000
	The relationship between individual and company performance	0.796	0.930	0.869	1.0000
	Career growth opportunities	0.981	0.883	0.915	1.0000
	Proud of the company	0.761	0.812	0.755	1.0000
	Coworkers/team members	0.853	0.834	0.869	1.0000

The validity of the questionnaire instrument in the study was confirmed with convergent validity shown in table 2. Each variable had a loading factor value above 0.5, indicating that talent management, work engagement, and organizational justice variables were accurately represented.

Discriminant validity was also met with an AVE value above 0.5. Additionally, composite reliability showed feasibility for hypothesis testing as all variables had a value over 0.70, as seen in the above table.

Hypotheses Testing

Table 3. Direct Impact

Hypothesis	Impact	Path Coefficients	t-test	Result
H1	Organizational justice ->> work engagement	0.652	11.991	Significant
H2	Talent management ->> work engagement	0.872	13.761	Significant

Observed in the data provided by table 3, it becomes apparent that the t-test value for hypothesis 1 exceeds the threshold of t-table 1.99; signifying a clear, considerable impact of organizational justice on employee work engagement. Additionally, the t-test applied to hypothesis 2 also surpasses the designated t-table 1.99, spotlighting a significant effect of talent management on employee job involvement.

5. Discussion

On Work Engagement, H1: Effect of Organizational Justice is apparent. The manner in which employees are treated in their workplace has a bearing on their level of engagement in their job. It is essential for companies to recognize the significance of fair treatment of their employees in promoting their level of engagement and productivity. In the absence of organizational justice, the morale of workers takes a hit which leads to a decrease in productivity levels. Therefore, it is important for companies to maintain a substantial level of organizational justice to keep their employees engaged and productive.

Employee job involvement is significantly impacted by the fairness perceived within an organization. As a result of job fairness, employees feel involved in the workplace. Various studies, including those conducted by Sarawati and Lie (2021), Inoue, et al (2009), Pirzada, et al (2020), and Storm, et al (2014), have reinforced the findings reported by Apriono, et al (2021) and Dong, et al (2017) that emphasize the importance of organizational justice in promoting employee involvement. Fair treatment within the organization is pivotal for employees to feel connected to their work.

Engagement in the workplace is a vital aspect of job satisfaction, and research has shown that effective talent management can positively impact this engagement. Various variables, such as employee development, recognition and rewards, and communication, play crucial roles in talent management and job engagement. Providing employees with opportunities to learn new skills, grow and advance their careers promote a sense of value and motivation. Furthermore, acknowledging employee contributions, whether through positive feedback, promotions, or other gestures, fosters a sense of recognition and job satisfaction. Clear and transparent communication about company goals and expectations is also essential in improving engagement levels. These talent management approaches can lead to a more engaged and fulfilled workforce, which can, in turn, positively impact the overall success of a company.

Well-managed talent management can increase employees' sense of work involvement, as seen from the results of calculations and hypothesis testing. This means that employee job involvement can be improved with good talent management practices. The findings of this study are in line with previous research conducted by Ali, et al (2019), and Barkhuizen, et al (2014).

6. Conclusions

Obtained results revealed that the incline and decline of employees' sense of work commitment were swayed by sufficient talent management and perceived procedural fairness. The study outcomes demonstrated that organizational justice had a noteworthy impact on job involvement. This implies that the more impartially the organization interacts with employees, the stronger employees' sense of engagement will be. Additionally, the outcomes indicated that talent management had a considerable influence on work commitment, meaning that if the organization executes better talent management, employees are likely to be more work engaged. Recommendations and suggestions for improvement can be crucial to progress. It is essential to consider outside guidance as it offers a fresh perspective on an existing problem. Seeking opinions from numerous sources can increase the likelihood of finding a solution. Improvements can come from unique viewpoints that have not yet been considered, and being open to these suggestions can expand growth. Asking for advice can establish an inclusive and open work environment where everyone feels comfortable offering their input. Only examining the influence of job fairness on work involvement, this study's limitation is apparent. However, the factors that contribute to organizational involvement are numerous, including but not limited to talent management, work motivation, competence, and empowerment.

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8392438>